

Milestone: M5.3 Harmonised economic modelling methodology

Lead Participant: Lygature

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Date Of Completion: 10 Nov 2022

Means of Verification

1+MG HEOR summary paper

When 1+MG/B1MG started, we anticipated the health economic field was evolving rather quickly in evaluating genomics/predictive diagnostics and hence were developing specific methodology. UK was known to be working on it (for rare diseases), but due to Brexit we do not have access to these developments directly (only from publications and informal interactions, and publications are delayed). In most of the other countries, national genome programs, if any, were only recently developed and only few have an integrated health economic plan (details are in development). Therefore, for this milestone, the 1+MG HEOR group decided to make an overview of initiatives in signatory countries and share best practices in order to work towards a more common approach for economic evaluation of genomics.

Project participants & others

1+MG HEOR WG members

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

Yes. Economic evaluation methodology of WGs is immature. Only few countries (France, UK, Estonia) are developing methodology.

Next action steps

Organise a workshop in May to define concrete recommendations for the EC for developing the HTA field for WGs.

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